

Artificial Intelligence in Education: A Bibliometric Analysis (2010–2021)

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Abstract—Given the growing importance of artificial intelligence in education (AIEd) and the increasing interest in its use and application, this study analyzes AIEd scientific output from publications registered with the Web of Science online database (2010–2021). A modified bibliometric research approach was used in the most critical social science databases. According to the findings, there is global interest in using AI in educational settings, indicating that this is a rapidly expanding field of study. Data on active participants may assist educators and scholars in connecting with other AIEd researchers and organizations to raise awareness of the significant challenges in the field.

Keywords—artificial intelligence, intelligence in education, AIEd, education

I. INTRODUCTION

The widespread use of AIEd is speeding up the processing of related research. Therefore, the body of relevant literature is rapidly expanding, resulting in an abundance of educational AI research. Despite this growing popularity, only a few bibliometric analyses focus on AI applications for specific types of problems. A bibliometric analysis of general education-related AI studies can create a map that allows researchers to better understand the evolution of AIEd research and the direction of patterns and trends. Keeping up with the rapidly expanding body of AIEd research will enable educators and policymakers to seize more opportunities to apply AI inventions and promote learning.

A bibliometric analysis provides researchers and other stakeholders with a comprehensive understanding of the field of study while encouraging interdisciplinary collaboration [6]. This research aims to provide a comprehensive overview of AIEd and a map for future development. This analysis seeks to examine AI research and promote education by reviewing the extensive international literature on AIEd. Thus, it is an essential resource for researchers and those unfamiliar with the field but who are interested in applying AIEd.

Analyzing trends in scientific publications in a given field can provide insights into the area's development, production, interest, and the advancement of scientific knowledge [4]. In general, an increase in publications indicates increased interest in AIEd [1]. Furthermore, the analysis of institutions and researchers assists scholars in identifying significant contributors to the field and enables them to share and exchange

research [5]. This study aims to answer the following four research questions:

1. What are the current trends in AIEd research?
2. How is AIEd research distributed globally?
3. Who are the active researchers in AIEd?
4. What are the most frequently used keywords in AIEd searches?

In many ways, this study also contributes to the field of research. First, it allows educators and scholars to understand the status and progress of relevant AIEd publications; second, it helps educators and scholars find active AIEd researchers and institutions; third, it raises educators' and scholars' awareness of the most commonly used keywords in AIEd studies, which is especially helpful when deciding what types of issues to address.

The rest of this article is organized as follows:

- The Materials and Methods section describes data collection and analysis related to AIEd characteristics.
- The Results section identifies publication years, article trends, top keywords, institutions, and researchers working in AIEd.
- The Discussion section summarizes the findings and emphasizes the significance and necessity of the researcher's work.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The most relevant documents were gathered from the Web of Science (WoS) databases using the advanced search query shown in Table 1 to analyze education-related AI studies.

TABLE I. DETAILS OF THE INSTITUTE FOR SCIENTIFIC INFORMATION SEARCH QUERY

Query	Detail
Topics	Artificial intelligence in education or AIEd
Publication years	2020–2021
Document types	Articles
Web of Science Categories	Education, educational research
Language	English

The WoS is the most popular database for studies with a bibliometric analysis [7]. The search detailed in Table 1 was conducted on December 6, 2021, and a total of 241 records were collected. These data helped develop an understanding of AIED’s current research status.

The active AIED researchers were identified based on citations offered by Google Scholar. The study included researchers interested in AIED with more than 1,500 citations.

III. RESULTS

A. AIED Article Publication Trends

The number of related publications from 2010 to 2021 is illustrated in Figure 1. The years in which publications were accessed from the WoS database are also listed. In total, 241 AIED papers (indexed in the WoS) were reviewed in this study. Figure 1 shows a progressive trend in published AIED-related papers from early 2010 to late 2021. Most papers (n = 85) were published in 2021, with 2020 (74 papers) and 2019 (38 papers) the second and third most productive years for AIED, respectively. As shown in Figure 1, the publication trend of AIED articles increased between 2010 and 2021.

Figure 1. The annual number of AIED-related publications (2010–2021)

B. Countries and Regions Generating AIED Publications

The locations of the major contributors to the 241 AIED publications were identified. The top 25 countries are presented in Table 2 and Figure 2. The most prolific country represented in AIED research was the USA (53 publications, 22.27%), followed by China (41 publications, 17.23%), and the UK (28 publications, 11.77%).

TABLE II. NUMBER OF AIED PUBLICATIONS BY REGION (2010–2021)

Rank	Country or Region	No. of Articles	%
1	USA	53	22.27%
2	China	41	17.23%
3	UK	28	11.77%
4	Taiwan	20	8.40%
5	Australia	15	6.30%
6	Canada	12	5.04%
7	Spain	12	5.04%
8	Russia	10	4.20%
9	Scotland	8	3.36%
10	Germany	7	2.94%
11	Turkey	7	2.94%
12	India	5	2.10%
13	Italy	5	2.10%
14	Japan	5	2.10%
15	Portugal	5	2.10%
16	Brazil	4	1.68%
17	Greece	4	1.68%
18	Malaysia	4	1.68%
19	Singapore	4	1.68%
20	Sweden	4	1.68%
21	Belgium	3	1.26%
22	The Netherlands	3	1.26%
23	Pakistan	3	1.26%
24	Saudi Arabia	3	1.26%
25	South Africa	3	1.26%

Figure 1. The number of AIED publications by region (2010–2021)

C. Active Researchers in AIED

Active AIED researchers are listed in Table 3.

TABLE III. RESEARCHERS ACTIVE IN AIED (2010–2021)

Author	Institution	Country
Gwo-Jen Hwang	Taiwan TECH	Taiwan
Stephen J H Yang	National Central University	Taiwan
James Lester	North Carolina State University	USA
Peter W. Foltz	University of Colorado	USA
Cristobal Romero	University of Cordoba	Spain
Diane Litman	University of Pittsburgh	USA
Riichiro Mizoguchi	Japan Advanced Institute of Science and Technology	Japan
Julita Vassileva	University of Saskatchewan	Canada
Beverly Park Woolf	University of Massachusetts	USA

Susan Bull	University of Birmingham	UK
Rose Luckin	University College London	UK
Antonija Mitrovic	University of Canterbury	New Zealand
Gordon McCalla	University of Saskatchewan	Canada
Haoran Xie	Lingnan University	Hong Kong
Kalina Yacef	University of Sydney	Australia
Jack Mostow	Carnegie Mellon University	USA
Seiji Isotani	University of Sao Paulo	Brazil
Johan Jeuring	Utrecht University	The Netherlands
Roger Nkambou	University of Quebec Montreal	Canada
Vania Dimitrova	University of Leeds	UK
Igbert Bittencourt	Federal University of Alagoas	Brazil
Vitomir Kovanović	University of South Australia	Australia
Vivekanandan Suresh Kumar	Athabasca University	Canada
Maria Mercedes T. Rodrigo	Ateneo de Manila University	Filipino
Eva Millán	Malaga University	Spain
Radek Pelánek	Masaryk University	Czech
Jonathan Rowe	North Carolina State University	USA
Diego Zapata-Rivera	Educational Testing Service	USA
Mark Core	University of Southern California	USA
Kristy Boyer	University of Florida	USA
Fuhua Lin	Athabasca University	Canada
Scott McQuiggan	SAS Institute	USA

Erin Shaw	USC Information Sciences Institute	USA
Jennifer Sabourin (Jennifer Robison)	North Carolina State University	USA

System	11	22
Information technology	6	21
Mathematics	5	21
Precision education	7	20
Educational technology	8	18
Chatbot	5	17
eLearning	12	16
Natural language processing	5	12
Pedagogy	7	12
Policy	5	8
Intelligent tutoring systems	7	6

D. Keywords Frequently Used in AIEd-related Publications

The analysis of keywords used in AIEd publications was carried out using VOSviewer, which generates a network map of terms or concepts frequently repeated in titles and abstracts. Table 4 and Figure 3 show the most commonly used keywords in the 241 AIEd publications studied. There were 102 instances of “artificial intelligence,” and “education” appeared 37 times. It is also worth noting that AI technologies, such as “machine learning,” “chatbot,” “data,” “neural network,” and “natural language processing” were frequently mentioned in the AIEd studies. This indicates a broad interest in applying AI technologies to resolve issues related to teaching and learning among scholars.

TABLE IV. TOP-RANKING KEYWORDS USED IN AIED PUBLICATIONS (2010–2021)

Keyword	No. of Occurrences	Total Link Strength
Artificial intelligence	102	193
Education	37	88
Science	13	49
Technology	15	47
Design	13	43
Big Data	14	41
Higher education	21	39
Learning analytics	11	37
Students	10	36
Performances	11	35
Machine learning	24	30
AI	8	28
Future	9	25
Automation	6	23
Assessment	7	22
Motivation	6	22

Figure 3. Top-ranking keywords used in AIED publications (2010–2021)

IV. DISCUSSION

Results show that the application of AIED is a reality because current research has obtained valuable results. According to the study's data, research in the AIED field entered a period of rapid development around 2020, and the number of AIED papers continues to grow. An examination of the findings reveals a broad interest in AIED among scholars from multiple fields.

The results reveal that educational technology from significant institutions in developed countries tends to dominate. Fifty-three AIED-related papers were published in the USA, 41 in China, and 28 in the UK, indicating that research on applying AIED appears to be linked to economic growth. There has also been a significant increase in interest and enthusiasm for this field in recent years. When a pandemic like COVID-19 disrupts regular teaching, there are numerous AI opportunities in adaptive learning technologies, virtual and augmented reality, analytics, data mining, precision education, and data-driven education [8]. As a result, international interest in AIED and scientific research is growing among educators, researchers, governments, and educational institutions.

The top keywords used in AIED publications show a broad interest in technical issues, including the use of a variety of AI technologies, such as machine learning, Big Data, natural

language processing, and learning analytics. Various applications and tools have been developed primarily with AI technologies, such as chatbots, intelligent tutoring systems, digital laboratories, virtual assistants, and personalized education. Issues concerning learners' motivations and attitudes toward their academic performance are of great interest to AIED scholars. Furthermore, several subfields of educational technology, such as automated governance, data privacy rights, learning analytics, and educational data mining, are frequently mentioned in AIED studies. Although these areas are closely related to AIED, it is recommended that research pioneers distinguish between them by identifying distinct research foci or issues to be highlighted. Although AIED scholars have shown a diverse range of interests in various AIED perspectives and topics, educational theories have received little attention. It is recommended that AIED researchers focus more on integrating educational theory and AI technologies. As a result, their research can be more profound and theoretically sound, with authoritative and well-recognized theories to back it up.

AIED research has yet to keep pace with the rapid advancements in AI technology and provide evidence-based guidelines and support for AI applications in education. Despite this progress, recent literature reviews reveal a lack of educational perspectives in AIED research [2], [3], [9].

Some AIED technologies have received more attention than others, e.g., much research has focused on intelligent tutors or personalized learning systems and environments. According to the results of this review, only a few research publications have examined the impact of chatbots or machine learning in education. As a result, future research should focus on a broader range of AIED technologies, particularly those that have received little attention in the past.

Finally, AIED research is quickly becoming one of the most hotly debated topics in computer science and education. This study hopes that academics from computer science and education backgrounds will be inspired to conduct further AIED research through this article.

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